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Processing of oxide bonded porous silicon carbide ceramic membrane for the treatment of oily wastewater

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Introduction: The demand for ceramic membrane from its various end-user industries is continuously showing an upward trend mainly due to the increasing demand for high purity filtration components in various applications. Among applications, the water & wastewater treatment, pharmaceuticals, chemical processing, etc. segment is expected to grow significantly. Today our water resources are threatened worldwide more than ever due to rapid population growth and industrialization and water-borne diseases kill nearly 12 million people every year. Modern human activities have however disrupted the balance between the usage and natural purification processes leading to a shortage of potable water. To meet the increasing demand for water wastewater needs to be purified and recycled. Ceramic membranes are considered a suitable filter for water filtration and purification due to their advantageous properties compared to polymeric membranes. Compared with other ceramic membranes such as titania, zirconia, etc., silicon carbide (SiC) is a promising material due to its higher hydrophilicity, lower fouling tendency, better resistance to chemicals, higher permeate fluxes in wastewater treatment. However, due to the covalent nature of the Si–C bonds, high sintering temperatures (~2000°C) are required for the production of SiC ceramics. The Oxide-bonding technique is considered a simple technique for the fabrication of porous SiC membranes [1] at a lower temperature. Oxidized SiC surface could lower water contact angle, improve the hydrophilic property and offer better water permeability.

Methods: Different amounts of SiC powders, bond phase additives (such as alumina, clay, silica, Y₂O₃, etc.), and pore formers were mixed homogeneously and then pressed into the disc and bar-shaped samples. After that, the green SiC samples were sintered at (1000-1400°C) via oxide bonding technique. The sintered membranes were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Pore size distribution (PSD) analysis; density and porosity were measured by Archimedes method. Oily wastewater was collected, and the filtration studies were carried out in a laboratory-made test setup.

Results & Discussions: Oxide bonded porous SiC ceramic membranes were fabricated at a comparatively lower sintering temperature (1000-1400°C) via oxide bonding technique using different bond phase additives. Moreover, industrial waste fly ash was recycled and used as a source of bonding phase additives. The porosity of the membranes was increased with the addition of pore formers to the final ceramics. XRD study showed that there is a formation of mullite phases for the composition. SEM analysis indicated the formation of porous microstructure with interconnected pores. The SiC particles were bonded through rod-type mullite and fish scale type cristobalite phases at neck regions. Depending on the processing parameters, the membrane showed an average pore diameter, porosity, pure water permeability, and strength in the range of ~1.3-6.5 μm, 31-58 vol%, 1532-13298 Lm⁻²h⁻¹bar⁻¹ and 12.47-38.40 MPa respectively. The results showed that depending on the porosity of the membrane ~77-93% oil, 89-94% turbidity, and 82-93% COD were removed from grey wastewater.

Conclusions: This study may provide a suitable method to produce high-valued SiC-based porous ceramic membranes at a comparatively lower temperature for potential oily wastewater separation.

Keywords: SiC membrane, Reaction Bonding, Fly ash, Oil-water filtration

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